

Board Committee Diversity and the Value Relevance of Accounting Information of Nigerian Banks

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Abstract

This study examined whether board committee diversity influenced the value relevance of accounting information in listed Nigerian commercial banks. Using an ex-post facto research design, the study analyzed data from the eight banks that have international authorization licenses between the period, 2018 – 2022. Board committee diversity was measured across three key committees: risk, remuneration and nomination and governance committees respectively; while share price was adopted as the proxy for value relevance. A census sampling approach was adopted, and the outcome of the diagnostic tests led to the adoption of the contemporaneous correlation technique as the appropriate estimation method for the test of the study's hypotheses. The results show that gender diversity within risk committees does not significantly influence the value relevance of accounting information. However, diversity in nomination and governance committees, as well as remuneration committees, exerts a significant positive effect on the value relevance of accounting information of listed commercial banks with international authorization license. These findings highlight the varying roles of board sub-structures in enhancing the informativeness of financial reports. The study recommends among others that Regulatory bodies such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should strengthen monitoring mechanisms to ensure that board committees; especially nomination and governance as well as remuneration committees, are constituted with appropriate levels of diversity and competence.

Keywords: Accounting, accounting information, corporate governance, financial reports, share price.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Board committee diversity has become a central theme in corporate governance discourse, with scholars emphasizing the importance of gender, expertise, professional experience, and other demographic attributes in shaping board effectiveness, firm performance, and decision-making quality (Morrone, Bianchi, Marsocci & Faioli, 2022; Lee & Thong, 2022). Despite this growing attention, the influence of board committee diversity on the value relevance of accounting information remains underexplored, particularly within emerging markets such as Nigeria; and a particular focus on commercial banks with international authorization license.

Accounting information is fundamental to capital markets, providing signals about organizations' performance, risk profile, and future prospects. The value relevance of accounting information which summarizes the extent to which financial statements and related disclosures influence investors' valuation decisions and share prices has become a widely used measure of reporting quality (Ikram, 2016; Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018; Tchaga, Cai & Ntezolo, 2023). While evidence from developed economies links board diversity to enhanced

governance practices and improved financial reporting outcomes, it is uncertain whether these findings extend to Nigeria's banking landscape, given country's unique socio-cultural, economic, and institutional dynamics.

Nigeria, as one of Africa's largest economy, has introduced governance reforms aimed at strengthening transparency, accountability, and investor confidence (Oyedokun, 2019; Ogieh & Jeroh, 2022). However, empirical studies in this context often focus narrowly on gender diversity at the board level, with limited attention to diversity within board committees or to other demographic attributes beyond gender (Onyekwere & Babangida, 2022). This narrow focus leaves significant knowledge gaps regarding how committee-level diversity affects financial reporting outcomes such as value relevance. Moreover, most prior studies fail to examine risk, nomination and governance, and remuneration committees, despite their central role in shaping firms' reporting and governance structures.

Addressing these gaps is critical for regulators, investors, and corporate stakeholders seeking evidence-based insights on how board structures shape the quality and informativeness of financial reports in emerging markets. Against this backdrop, this study investigates the relationship between board committee diversity and the value relevance of accounting information among listed Nigerian commercial banks. Specifically, it assesses whether diversity within risk management, nomination and governance, and remuneration committees influences the value relevance of financial reports, as proxied by share price. The study draws on data from eight internationally licensed commercial banks between 2018 and 2022, a period following the introduction of Nigeria's 2018 Code of Corporate Governance. By focusing on committee-level diversity, this study contributes to corporate governance literature in emerging economies and provides practical insights for enhancing transparency, accountability, and investor decision-making.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Value Relevance

The concept of value relevance has become central in accounting, finance, and investment research, particularly in evaluating the usefulness of financial information for decision-making. It refers to the extent to which accounting numbers (earnings, book value, or cash flows, etc) explain or predict variations in a firm's stock price or other measures of economic worth (Ikram, 2016; Tchaga, Cai & Ntezolo, 2023). In this sense, accounting information is deemed value relevant when it provides investors with insights that influence their valuation and investment choices (Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019; Ighosewe, 2022).

The underlying assumption is market efficiency, where stock prices reflect available information, and any change in financial reporting should correspond with observable movements in market value. Value relevance therefore depends on financial statements being not only timely but also relevant and reliable. Investors, creditors, and other stakeholders rely on the accuracy and transparency of reported numbers to assess firms' performance and prospects (Bahri-Sales, Behnamoon & Hoseinzadeh, 2013; Ayadi & Boujelbene, 2015).

Empirical studies typically assess value relevance by statistically testing the association between accounting figures and share prices, using regression and correlation analyses. Such

research highlights the role of financial reporting in fostering efficient capital markets, strengthening investor confidence, and guiding resource allocation.

2.1.2 Concept of Board Committee Diversity

Board committee diversity extends the broader principle of board diversity by emphasizing heterogeneity within specialized subcommittees (risk, remuneration and nomination and governance committees). It refers to the inclusion of individuals with varied demographic attributes, professional expertise, and perspectives to enhance oversight, decision-making, and governance effectiveness (Morrone, Bianchi, Marsocci & Faioli, 2022; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024).

Diversity can be demographic, encompassing gender, age, ethnicity, nationality, and cultural background, or professional, reflecting expertise in areas such as finance, law, human resources, technology, and operations. A heterogeneous committee composition ensures that multiple viewpoints are considered, enabling more comprehensive oversight and informed decisions. For example, risk committees benefit from members with backgrounds in accounting, investment, and risk management, while technology committees may require expertise in cybersecurity, analytics, and information technology systems.

Evidence suggests that diverse committees contribute to stronger financial performance, more robust risk management, and enhanced innovation, while also improving legitimacy and stakeholder trust (Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020; Braendle, Stiglbauer, Ababneh & Dedousis, 2020). Thus, board committee diversity has emerged as a governance mechanism with implications for organizational performance and reporting quality.

2.2 Board Committee Diversity and Value Relevance of Accounting Information

While extensive scholarship has examined the relationship between board diversity and firm outcomes such as performance, value, and reporting quality (Jeroh, 2020; Ogieh & Jeroh, 2022; Morrone, Bianchi, Marsocci & Faioli, 2022), research specifically linking board committee diversity to the value relevance of accounting information remains limited, particularly in emerging economies. Nigerian studies, for example, have largely concentrated on gender diversity at the board level, often overlooking committee-level dynamics and other dimensions of diversity such as expertise and religious affiliation (Onyekwere & Babangida, 2022; Owolabi, Bamsaye, Efuntade & Efuntade, 2021). This narrow focus creates a gap in understanding how heterogeneous board committees may influence the informativeness of financial statements (Oyedokun, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2025).

Since committee structures directly shape decisions around risk oversight, governance nominations, and remuneration, their diversity may significantly affect the credibility and market responsiveness of reported numbers. Yet, empirical evidence addressing this relationship in Nigeria remains scarce.

By investigating how gender, professional expertise, and religious affiliation within key board committees influence the value relevance of accounting information, this study contributes to bridging this gap. It offers insights into how committee-level diversity shapes investors' valuation processes and strengthens corporate governance in Nigeria's financial sector.

2.3 Conceptual Model

This study designs a conceptual framework that links board committee diversity to value relevance of accounting information. Diversity within risk management, nomination and governance, and remuneration committees is hypothesized to influence the informativeness of

financial reports, proxied by share price. The model (Fig. 1) illustrates these hypothesized associations.

Fig.1: Conceptual Model of the Study

Given the study’s focus and in line with the conceptual model in Fig.1, the following hypotheses were thus postulated and presented in their null forms to guide this study:

- H01:** There is no significant relationship between diversity in risk management committees of corporate boards and the value relevance of accounting information of listed Nigerian commercial banks.
- H02:** Governance and nominations committees’ diversity does not have significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information of listed Nigerian commercial banks.
- H03:** Remuneration committees’ diversity does not have significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information of listed Nigerian commercial banks.

2.4 Review of Empirical Studies

Empirical evidence on board diversity, corporate governance, and financial reporting outcomes reveals mixed but insightful patterns across contexts. In developed economies, studies often highlight the positive role of diversity in reducing financial distress and improving market outcomes. For example, Jia (2019), using panel 2SLS regression on Australian firms, found that the proportion of financially skilled women on risk management committees significantly reduced the likelihood of financial distress. Similarly, Zhou (2019) reported that Chinese firms with female directors were less prone to insolvency and enjoyed greater access to bank financing, suggesting that gender diversity strengthens resilience and investor confidence. In a cross-country study, Lee and Thong (2022) reported that gender-diverse boards enhanced performance and lowered financial distress risks, especially in countries with strong securities regulation and shareholder rights. These findings underscore the contextual importance of institutional environments in shaping the diversity – performance link.

Evidence from emerging markets is more nuanced. Hussain and Hanefah (2012), examining Malaysian firms, found that directors' shareholdings increased the value relevance of accounting information, while CEO duality diminished it, and female representation on boards had no significant effect. In Africa, Odubuasi, Offor and Ugbah (2022) documented that risk committee expertise and diligence significantly influenced bank performance in Nigeria, South Africa, and Ghana, emphasizing the importance of functional competence over demographic representation.

Within Nigeria, studies have largely concentrated on gender diversity at the board level rather than committee structures. Onyekwere and Babangida (2022) found that gender diversity improved return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) among banks, while excessive board independence reduced performance, aligning with agency and resource dependence theory. More recent evidence by Ibiamke, Tauhid and Okpanachi (2023) suggests that gender diversity in risk management committees significantly lowers financial distress risk in Nigerian banks, reflecting the governance reforms introduced by the 2018 Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance. Tchaga, Cai, and Ntezolo (2023), using data from Nigeria and Ghana, further demonstrated that corporate governance mechanisms such as independence and expertise enhance the value relevance of accounting information, particularly under IFRS disclosure requirements.

Overall, the literature reveals three key insights. First, board diversity (especially gender) has generally positive associations with financial stability, performance, and reporting quality, though effects vary by institutional setting. Second, in emerging markets, expertise and committee functionality often matter more than demographic attributes alone. Third, Nigerian studies remain limited in scope, focusing predominantly on gender and overall board composition while overlooking committee-level diversity and its implications for the value relevance of accounting information. Addressing this gap, the present study explores how diversity across risk management, nomination and governance, and remuneration committees influences the value relevance of accounting information in Nigerian commercial banks.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study employs an *ex-post facto* research design, relying on archival accounting data from audited financial statements. The population consists of all Nigerian commercial banks with international authorization licenses as of 31 December 2022 ($n = 8$). A census approach was adopted, and all banks were included in the sample. Data were obtained from secondary sources, specifically annual reports covering 2018–2022, a period that spans the implementation of the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (2018). The empirical analysis follows a quantitative approach. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) were computed, followed by correlation analysis and diagnostic testing. Hypotheses were tested using panel regression estimated with panel-corrected standard errors (PCSE) to address heteroscedasticity and related concerns.

3.1 Model Specification

In the light of the conceptual model which is based on the specific objectives of this study, the following econometric model was designed to inform the analytic step for the study's hypotheses testing.

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RMCD_{it} + \beta_2 NGCD_{it} + \beta_3 RCD_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

[1]

The *a-priori* expectation which is in the light of research outcome evinced in prior empirical documentation is that $\beta_1 X_{1it} < 0$, $\beta_2 X_{2it} < 0$, $\beta_3 X_{3it} < 0$.

3.2. Measurement of the Study’s Variables

Table 3.1 below shows how the variables of interest were operationalized:

Table 3.1: Operationalization of Study Variables

S/N	Variables	Labels and Measures	Nature of Variable	Measurement	Apriori Expectations
1	Value Relevance	SP (Share Price)	Dependent Variable	Average share price for of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>	Positive
2	Risk Management Committee Diversity (RMCD)	RMCG - Risk Management Committee Gender RMCE - Risk Management Committee Expertise RMCRA - Risk Management Committee Religious Affiliation	Regressors	Proportion of women presence in the risk management committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> Proportion of members with professional qualifications in finance and related fields in the risk management committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> Proportion of members who are Muslims in the risk management committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>	Positive
3	Nomination and Governance Committee Diversity (NGCD)	NGCG – Nomination and Gov. Committee Gender NGCE – Nomination and Gov. Committee Expertise NGCRA – Nomination and Gov. Committee Religious Affiliation	Regressors	Proportion of women presence in the nomination & governance committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> Proportion of members with professional qualifications in finance and related fields in the nomination & governance committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> Proportion of members who are Muslims in the nomination and governance committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>	Positive
4	Remuneration Committee Diversity (RCD)	RCG – Remuneration Committee Gender RCE – Remuneration Committee Expertise RCRA – Remuneration Committee Religious Affiliation	Regressors	Proportion of women presence in the remuneration committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> Proportion of members with professional qualifications in finance and related fields in the remuneration committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> Proportion of members who are Muslims in the remuneration committee of bank <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>	Positive

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2024).

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Data Presentation

This research examines the effect of board committee diversity on the value relevance of accounting information. Considering the fact that banks are highly regulated due to the existence of several regulators with simultaneous oversights on banks' activities, the focus of this study was specifically tailored at commercial banks operating in Nigeria. The data collated from the sampled banks covers 5 years (2018 -2022). The list of the banks is indicated in Appendix I.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Statistics

The relevant summary statistics that describe the nature of the collated data for this research have been presented in this section. In view of the descriptive statistics, the outcome analysed in this section include results for mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values. Table 4.1 the analytical outcomes for the descriptive statistics.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
SP	40	11.247	9.753	1.85	34.45
RMCG	40	0.259	0.218	0.00	0.75
RMCE	40	0.515	0.134	0.273	0.857
RM CRA	40	0.153	0.165	0.00	0.60
NGCG	40	0.398	0.285	0.00	1.00
NGCE	40	0.475	0.075	0.333	0.667
NG CRA	40	0.224	0.148	0.00	0.50
RCG	40	0.138	0.217	0.00	0.75
RCE	40	0.171	0.233	0.00	0.75
RCRA	40	0.063	0.130	0.00	0.50

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of the study variables based on 40 observations, derived from eight banks over five years, constituting a balanced panel dataset. The sample size exceeds the conventional threshold of 30 observations recommended for valid regression analysis (Gujarati & Porter, 2009), confirming the adequacy of the data for subsequent econometric tests.

The mean values range from 0.063 for Remuneration Committees' Religious Affiliation (RCRA) to 11.247 for Share Price (SP), with corresponding standard deviations of 0.130 and 9.753, respectively. The relatively low standard deviations indicate minimal dispersion around the mean, suggesting data consistency across the sample period.

Minimum values of zero for RMCG, NGCG, and RCG imply that, in some years, certain banks' board committees had no female representation. Similarly, zeros for RM CRA, NG CRA, and RCRA indicate an absence of members with Islamic affiliations in some banks, while a minimum of zero for RCE suggests that certain remuneration committees lacked members with professional qualifications in finance or related fields. These variations underscore the diversity in board composition among Nigerian commercial banks and provide a preliminary indication of governance heterogeneity relevant to subsequent regression analysis.

4.2.2 Test For Normality of Data

In order to ascertain the distribution of the data and to establish whether the data followed a normal curve, the Shapiro-Wilk test for normal data was conducted. This is necessary to determine the existence or otherwise of inconsistencies in respect of the basic assumptions for the application of the OLS regression method. The outcome in this regard is displayed in Table 4.2

Table 4.2 Normality Test Outcome

Variables	Obs.	W	V	Z	Prob>Z
SP	40	0.79629	8.052	4.39	0.00001
RMCG	40	0.94348	2.234	1.691	0.04538
RMCE	40	0.97579	0.957	-0.092	0.53675
RM CRA	40	0.87329	5.009	3.391	0.00035
NGCG	40	0.97192	1.110	0.219	0.41314
NGCE	40	0.98274	0.682	-0.804	0.78932
NG CRA	40	0.97982	0.798	-0.476	0.68302
RCG	40	0.8344	6.546	3.954	0.00004
RCE	40	0.86376	5.385	3.543	0.00002
RCRA	40	0.75979	9.495	4.737	0.00000

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4.2 reports the results of the Shapiro–Wilk test for normality at the 5% significance level. Under this test, a variable’s residuals are considered normally distributed if the associated p -value ($\text{Prob} > Z$) exceeds 0.05. Conversely, p -values below 0.05 indicate departures from normality. The results show that the residuals for RMCE, NGCG, NGCE, and NG CRA exhibit p -values greater than 0.05, confirming that these variables follow a normal distribution. However, the residuals for SP, RMCG, RM CRA, RCG, RCE, and RCRA returned p -values below 0.05, suggesting deviations from normality.

The mixed outcome implies that while some variables satisfy the normality assumption, others violate it. Given that the classical Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique assumes normally distributed residuals for unbiased and efficient estimates, these findings necessitate the adoption of a more robust estimation approach. Accordingly, regression techniques that correct for non-normality and heteroscedasticity – such as the Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) is considered more appropriate for hypothesis testing in this study.

4.2.3 Correlation Analysis

In examining the link between measures of board committee diversity and value relevance of accounting information the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho) was adopted since the residuals for some of the data did not follow a normal distribution curve. The outcome for the Spearman rho is presented in Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Correlation Analysis

	sp	rmcg	rmce	rmcra	ngcg	ngce	ngcra	rcg	rce	rcra
sp	1.0000									
rmcg	-0.0243	1.0000								
rmce	-0.0774	-0.0125	1.0000							
rmcra	0.1365	-0.3251*	0.2249	1.0000						
ngcg	0.0398	0.4651*	0.1664	-0.2524	1.0000					
ngce	0.0210	-0.1788	0.4326*	0.1608	-0.0059	1.0000				
ngcra	0.1805	0.1816	0.3600*	0.3722*	0.3052	0.1240	1.0000			
rcg	-0.2534	0.2835	-0.2793	-0.1541	0.1316	-0.0451	-0.0349	1.0000		
rce	-0.3611*	0.2057	-0.2045	-0.1673	-0.0141	0.1328	-0.2040	0.8656*	1.0000	
rcra	-0.5589*	0.1988	0.0581	0.0325	0.1115	0.0707	0.1538	0.6677*	0.7539*	1.0000

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

*significant at 5%

Table 4.3 presents the results of the correlation analysis, which examines the degree and direction of linear association among the study variables. The results indicate that Share Price (SP) exhibits negative correlations with RMCG, RMCE, RCG, RCE, and RCRA, suggesting that increases in these governance attributes are associated with declines in share price. Conversely, SP shows positive correlations with RMCRA, NGCG, NGCE, and NGCRA, implying that higher representation of these characteristics is linked to improved market valuation. The signs of the coefficients therefore reflect the nature of association - positive coefficients indicating direct relationships and negative coefficients indicating inverse relationships.

In assessing potential multicollinearity among the explanatory variables, it is observed that, apart from the correlation between RCE and RCG (0.8656), all other pairwise correlation coefficients fall below the conventional threshold of 0.80 (Odjaremu & Jeroh, 2019; Ozegbe & Jeroh, 2022; Izukwe & Jeroh, 2022). This suggests an absence of severe multicollinearity in the dataset. However, to further validate this observation, the variance inflation factor (VIF) test was conducted, providing a more robust diagnostic of multicollinearity prior to the regression estimation.

4.2.4 Tests for Multicollinearity and Heteroscedasticity

To ascertain whether or not the data have outliers, the VIF test was conducted along with the test for heteroscedasticity. The outcome is presented in Table 4.4a and 4.4b.

Table 4.4a: Result for Multicollinearity Test

Variables	VIF	1/VIF
RCG	4.88	0.204709
RCE	4.16	0.240618
RCRA	3.24	0.308277
NGCRA	2.22	0.449819
RMCRA	2.08	0.480815
RMCE	1.85	0.541711
RMCG	1.79	0.558040
NGCG	1.71	0.585147
NGCE	1.69	0.593432
Mean VIF	2.62	

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 4.4b: Test for Heteroscedasticity

Breusch-Pagan /Cook-Weisberg Test	
Chi2(1)	9.55
Prob > chi2	0.0020

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

With the results in Table 4.4a, the values for VIF ranged from 1.69 (for NGCE) to 4.88 (for RCG). The mean VIF obtained was 2.62 which is below the maximum threshold of 10. This means that despite the high correlation between RCE and RCG, the suspicion of multicollinearity does not stand and hence the inclusion of both variables in the study estimation models would not have significant influence on the likely regression outcome.

With respect to the test for heteroscedasticity, it is observed that the chi2(1) obtained was 9.55 with a corresponding p-value of 0.0020, thus indicating the absence of constant variance in the residuals and the likely presence of standard errors in the estimations. This result confirms the earlier stand of the outcome of the normality test.

Given the outcome of the above estimations, it is obvious that the OLS regression method is not appropriate for the test of hypotheses of this study. Thus, in testing the formulated hypotheses, this study therefore adopts a more appropriate statistical tool that can correct the standard errors inherent in the estimation. For this purpose, the contemporaneous correlation technique that applies regression analysis with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) was employed for the test of the formulated hypotheses.

4.3. Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Hypothesis One

Table 4.5: Regression Outcome For Hypothesis One

SP	Coeff.	Std. Err.	z	P > z 	Decision
RMCG	4.0442	6.8815	0.59	0.557	Do Not Reject Null Hypothesis
RMCE	-3.5096	6.6632	-0.53	0.598	
RM CRA	11.5552	10.0758	1.15	0.251	
_CONS	10.2428	2.5567	4.01	0.000	
Obs.			40		
Wald chi2(3)			3.02		
Prob > chi2			0.3881		
R-Squared			0.0332		

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

With the results for the test of hypothesis one which is presented in Table 4.5, RMCG and RM CRA recorded positive coefficients which means that they have positive association with the value relevance of accounting information which in this case is measured with reference to share price movement (SP). Conversely, RMCE which obtained a negative coefficient of -3.5096 is believed to have negative association with share price. The standard errors are low in each case, thereby suggesting high level of reliance on the estimations and models. With respect to the z-statistics which recorded 0.59, -0.53 and 1.14 for RMCG, RMCE and RM CRA

respectively with corresponding probability values of 0.557, 0.598 and 0.251, it is obvious that each dimension of risk committee diversity cannot singlehandedly influence share price.

In addition to the above, the result of the Wald chi2 (3) was 3.02 with a corresponding probability of 0.3881 meaning that at 5% significance level, the measures of risk committee diversity do not exert significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information. What this means is that this study cannot reject the null hypothesis that risk committee diversity does not have significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria.

4.3.2 Hypothesis Two

Table 4.6: Regression Outcome For Hypothesis Two

SP	Coeff.	Std. Err.	z	P > z	Decision
NGCG	-7.0651	2.4017	-2.94	0.003	Reject Null Hypothesis
NGCE	-10.7941	10.9958	-0.98	0.326	
NGCRA	15.1948	5.9420	2.56	0.011	
_CONS	15.7835	4.5422	3.47	0.001	
Obs.			40		
Wald chi2(3)			11.48		
Prob > chi2			0.0094		
R-Squared			0.0735		

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Going by the results for the test of hypothesis two which is presented in Table 4.6, NGCG and NGCE recorded negative coefficients which means that they have negative association with share price which was used as proxy for the value relevance of accounting information in this study. Conversely, NGCRA which obtained a positive coefficient of 15.1948 is believed to have positive association with share price. The standard errors obtained for all variables are low, thus indicating that the estimations and models of the study with respect to hypothesis two are highly reliable and with precision.

With respect to the results of the z-statistics, NGCG, NGCE and NGCRA had -2.94, -0.98 and 2.56 respectively with corresponding probability values of 0.003, 0.326 and 0.011. This means that gender and religious affiliation diversity in nomination and governance committees respectively can separately influence share price singlehandedly. This is not the case for nomination and governance committee expertise.

In addition to the above, the result of the Wald chi2 (3) was 11.48 with a corresponding probability of 0.0094 meaning that at 5% significance level, the measures of nomination and governance committee diversity exerts significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information among Nigerian banks. What this means is that this study rejects the null hypothesis that nomination and governance committee diversity does not have significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria.

4.3.2 Hypothesis Three

Table 4.7: Regression Outcome For Hypothesis Three

SP	Coeff.	Std. Err.	z	P > z	Decision
RCG	24.4168	7.8226	3.12	0.002	
RCE	-6.8366	4.7236	-1.45	0.148	Reject Null
RCRA	-51.8189	14.4128	-3.60	0.000	Hypothesis
_CONS	12.2790	0.8231	14.92	0.000	
Obs.			40		
Wald chi2(3)			47.23		
Prob > chi2			0.0000		
R-Squared			0.2220		

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

An analysis of the results for the test of hypothesis three which is presented in Table 4.7 reveals that RCE and RCRA recorded negative coefficients of -6.8366 and -51.8189 respectively. This means that RCE and RCRA have negative relationship with share price. Conversely, remuneration committee gender diversity (RCG) obtained a positive coefficient of 24.4168 thus indicating that the relationship between remuneration committee gender diversity and share price movement is positive. The standard errors obtained for all variables are low, which also implies that the estimations and models of the study with respect to hypothesis three are highly reliable and with precision.

With respect to the results of the z-statistics, RCG, RCE and RCRA had 3.12, -1.45 and -3.60 respectively with corresponding probability values of 0.002, 0.148 and 0.000. This means that gender and religious affiliation diversity in remuneration committees respectively can separately influence share price singlehandedly. This is not the case for remuneration committee expertise.

In addition to the above, the result of the Wald chi2 (3) was 47.23 with a corresponding probability of 0.0000 meaning that at 5% significance level, the measures of remuneration committee diversity exert significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information among Nigerian banks. What this means is that this study rejects the null hypothesis that remuneration committee diversity does not have significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria.

4.4 Discussion of Results

This study examined the relationship between diversity in corporate board committees and the value relevance of accounting information among Nigerian commercial banks with international authorization license. Diversity was operationalized along three dimensions (gender, expertise, and religious affiliation) and its effects were evaluated across three key board committees: risk management, nomination and governance, and remuneration committees respectively. The hypotheses were tested at a 5% significance level using the contemporaneous correlation framework with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSE) to ensure robust estimation.

The results for the first hypothesis revealed that diversity within the risk management committee does not have a statistically significant effect on the value relevance of accounting

information (Wald $\chi^2(3) = 3.02, p = 0.3881$). This suggests that variations in gender, expertise, and religious representation within the risk management committee are not sufficiently strong to influence how investors perceive the usefulness of accounting information in these banks. The finding contrasts with prior evidence by Ibiameke, Tauhid, and Okpanachi (2023), who reported a significant association between board risk committee diversity and firm value. A possible explanation for this divergence may lie in contextual differences in risk governance practices and the relatively conservative composition of Nigerian bank boards, where regulatory compliance may outweigh diversity considerations in shaping disclosure quality.

Conversely, the findings for the second hypothesis show that diversity within the nomination and governance committee significantly influences the value relevance of accounting information (Wald $\chi^2(3) = 11.48, p = 0.0094$). This result implies that greater heterogeneity in gender, expertise, and religious affiliation within this committee enhances the informativeness of reported accounting numbers, potentially through improved oversight and more inclusive governance processes. The finding corroborates prior studies (Onyekwere & Babangida, 2022; Owolabi, Bamisaye, Efuntade & Efuntade, 2021; Ibiameke, Tauhid & Okpanachi, 2023) that emphasize the strategic role of nomination and governance committees in shaping board composition and, by extension, the quality and transparency of financial reporting.

Similarly, the results for the third hypothesis demonstrate that measures of remuneration committee diversity exerts a statistically significant joint effect on the value relevance of accounting information (Wald $\chi^2(3) = 47.23, p < 0.001$). This finding suggests that diverse remuneration committees; particularly those integrating varied professional expertise and perspectives, enhance the credibility of compensation policies and promote the alignment of managerial incentives with shareholder interests. The result aligns with previous evidence (Taljaard, Ward & Muller, 2015; García-Izquierdo, Fernández-Méndez & Arrondo-García, 2018), which underscores the importance of committee heterogeneity in strengthening board monitoring and ensuring value-relevant disclosures.

Overall, the findings highlight that the impact of board committee diversity on the value relevance of accounting information is not uniform across governance structures. While diversity within risk management committees appears neutral, diversity in nomination and remuneration committees contributes significantly to improving the market's perception of accounting information quality. These results provide empirical support for agency and resource dependence theories, suggesting that diverse boards not only enhance decision-making quality but also improve the informational content of financial reports through more effective governance mechanisms.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the influence of board committee diversity on the value relevance of accounting information among listed commercial banks in Nigeria, focusing on the post-implementation period of the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG, 2018). Using data obtained from audited financial statements of banks with international authorization licenses for the period 2018–2022, the study employed descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to evaluate how diversity within key board committees affects the market's response to accounting information.

Empirical evidence revealed that diversity within risk management committees does not exert a statistically significant influence on the value relevance of accounting information. In contrast, diversity within nomination and governance committees and remuneration committees significantly and positively affect value relevance. These findings highlight the differentiated roles of board committees in strengthening the governance–reporting nexus, suggesting that diversity enhances oversight quality and strategic decision-making, particularly in committees directly involved with board renewal, executive evaluation, and remuneration policies.

Theoretically, the study advances the discourse on corporate board heterogeneity and financial reporting quality by emphasizing the committee-level perspective – an often-underexplored dimension in governance research. It provides empirical support for the argument that committee composition, when characterized by gender balance, professional expertise, and varied experience, fosters more effective monitoring and decision processes, thereby improving the credibility and informativeness of financial disclosures. This insight is particularly relevant for emerging economies, where institutional frameworks and governance practices continue to evolve.

This study therefore underscores that the effectiveness and legitimacy of board governance depend not only on structural compliance but also on the quality of diversity within committees. Well-composed and functionally diverse committees enhance the informational value of financial reporting, strengthen investor confidence, and reinforce the credibility of corporate governance systems in Nigeria’s banking sector and beyond.

From a policy and practical standpoint, the study recommends thus:

- i. Regulatory bodies such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should strengthen monitoring mechanisms to ensure that board committees; especially nomination and governance as well as remuneration committees, are constituted with appropriate levels of diversity and competence.
- ii. Corporate boards should view diversity as a strategic governance resource rather than a mere compliance requirement. Board committees should incorporate individuals with diverse gender, professional, and experiential backgrounds to enhance oversight effectiveness and reporting credibility.
- iii. Governance frameworks such as the NCCG (2018) should be revised to include explicit provisions on committee-level diversity, outlining clear benchmarks for inclusion and periodic evaluation of diversity outcomes.
- iv. Future research should extend this inquiry across sectors and jurisdictions, explore longitudinal data, and integrate broader dimensions of diversity—such as cognitive or ethnic diversity—to deepen understanding of how governance structures shape financial reporting value relevance.

REFERENCES

- Ayadi, W. M. & Y. Boujelbène. (2015). Internal governance mechanisms and value relevance of accounting earnings, an empirical study in the French context, *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 7(1), 3-25.
- Bahri-Sales, J., Behnamoon Y., & Hoseinzadeh G. H. (2013). Board of directors' characteristics and value relevance of accounting information in Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE), *Journal of Accounting Knowledge and Management Auditing*, 2(6), 51-63.
- Braendle, U., Stiglbauer, M., Ababneh, K. & Dedousis, E. (2020). The impact of board diversity on firm performance – the case of Germany. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 17(2), 183- 193. <http://doi.org/10.22495/cocv17i2art15>
- García-Izquierdo A. L., Fernández-Méndez, C, & Arrondo-García, R. (2018). Gender diversity on boards of directors and remuneration committees: The influence on listed companies in Spain. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9:1351. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01351.
- Hussain, H. K. & Hanefah, M. M. (2012). Board of directors' characteristics and value relevance of accounting information in Malaysian shariah-compliant companies: A panel data analysis. *Economics and Finance Review*, 2(6), 31-44.
- Ibiamke S.S., Tauhid S., Okpanachi S. (2023) Risk management committee gender and likelihood of financial distress of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 11(11), 59-73
- Ighosewe, E. F. (2022). Accounting information and value relevance: A quinquennial comparison of pre-and post-IFRS adoption of listed firms in Nigeria and South Africa. *Modern Economy*, 13(7), 1006-1023.
- Ikram, Z. (2016). Corporate governance and value relevance of accounting information: Evidence from Pakistan. *M.Sc. Thesis, Capital University of Science and Technology Islamabad*. Available at <https://thesis.cust.edu.pk/UploadedFiles/Zahid%20Ikram-MM141018.pdf>
- Izukwe, R. & Jeroh, E. (2022). Auditors' attributes and firm value of listed Nigerian service firms. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 4(4), 218-230.
- Jeroh, E. (2020). Corporate financial attributes and the value of listed financial service firms: The Nigerian evidence. *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 24(2), 1-13.
- Jia, J. (2019). Does risk management committee gender diversity matter? A financial distress perspective. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 34(8), 1050–1072. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-05-2018-1874>
- Lee, K. W., & Thong, T. Y. (2022). Board gender diversity, firm performance and corporate financial distress risk: international evidence from tourism industry. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EDI-11-2021-0283>

- Morrone, C., Bianchi, M. T., Marsocci, V. & Faioli, D. (2022). Board diversity and firm performance: An empirical analysis of Italian small-medium enterprise. *Corporate Ownership & Control*, 19(3), 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cocv19i3art1>.
- Naburgi, M.M., Ojo, L.O., & Oyedokun, G.E. (2024). Board Attributes and Risk Disclosure of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies Listed in Nigerian Exchange Group. *Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)*, 9(1), 40-56, a publication of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria
- Odjaremu, G. O. & Jeroh, E. (2019). Audit committee attributes and the reporting timeliness of listed Nigerian firms. *Trends Economics and Management*, 13(34), 69-82.
- Odubuasi, A. , Ofor, N. and Ugbah, A. (2022) Risk committee effectiveness and financial performance indicator of quoted firms in selected African countries. *Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 11, 634-647. doi: [10.4236/jfrm.2022.113030](https://doi.org/10.4236/jfrm.2022.113030).
- Ogieh, A. S. & Jeroh, E. (2022). Corporate governance and the value relevance of earnings. *Himalayan Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 3(5), 55-63.
- Onyekwere, S. C. & Babangida, N. I. (2022). Board diversity and firm performance: Panel data evidence from 12 selected commercial banks in Nigeria. *Daengku: Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Innovation* 2(1), 28-53. <https://doi.org/10.35877/454RI.daengku587>
- Owolabi, T. J., Bamisaye, T. O., Efuntade, A. O., & Efuntade, O. O. (2021). Board diversity and financial performance of quoted firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 5, 46-62
- Oyedokun, G. E. (2019). Board characteristics and financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Accounting & Taxation review*, official Journal of the International Accounting and Taxation Research Group, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Benin, Nigeria.
- Oyedokun, G. E., & Nwaokolobia, B. O. & Andah, A, R. (2019). Board gender diversity and performance of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Financial Sustainability Reporting (RJFSR)* 4(2), 1-12. A publication of the Department of Accountancy, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science & Technology
- Oyedokun, G. E., Micah, E. E. M., & Gimba, J.T. (2020). Effect of Board Attributes on Dividend Policies of Quoted Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. A paper presented at British Academy of Management BAM2020 Conference at Alliance Manchester Business School, Manchester, United Kingdom, 2-4 September 2020.
- Oyedokun, G.E., Oyedokun, D.M., & Oyedokun, P.O., (2025). Cultural Communication and Stakeholders' Engagement in the Nigerian Financial Reporting Landscape: A Two-Decade Contextual Analysis. In. K.A. Adeyemo, O. Campbell & O. Adepoju (Eds.). Two Decade of Lead City University, Ibadan: Management and Social Sciences Perspective to contemporary issues in Nigeria. A publication of the Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan. 41- 56. ISBN-978-978-775-786-4
- Ozegbe, K. K. & Jeroh, E. (2022). Audit quality and the financial performance of quoted companies in Nigeria: Empirical discourse. *Acta Universitatis Danubius Oeconomica*, 18(5), 182-197.

- Taljaard, C. C/ H., Ward, M. J. D. & Muller, C. J. (2015). Board diversity and financial performance: A graphical time-series approach, *South African Journal of Economic and Management Science*, 18(3), 425-448 <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajems.v18i3.926>
- Tchaga, S. T., Cai, C. & Ntezolo, C. N. (2023). Impact of corporate governance on value relevance: A comparative analysis using West African Stock Exchanges *Proceedings International Conference on Business, Economics & Management for Sustainable Future*, July 18.
- Umar-Dauda, S. L. & Oyedokun, G. E. (2018). Impact assessment of tax audit on tax compliance: A case study of Katsina State Board of Internal Revenue. *AE-FUNAI Journal of Accounting, Business and Finance (FJABAF)*, 3(1), 54-61. A bi-annual Journal of the Department of Accountancy, Business and Administration, Banking & Finance, Alex-Ekwueme Federal University of Ndufu-Alike, Ebonyi State Nigeria. Available at <https://www.fujabf.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/5.pdf>
- Zhou, G. (2019). Financial distress prevention in China: Does gender of board of directors matter? *Journal of Applied Finance & Banking*, 9(6), 127-153.

APPENDIX I

LIST OF SAMPLED BANKS

S/N	Names of Banks
1	ACCESS BANK PLC
2	FIDELITY BANK PLC.
3	FIRST BANK HOLDINGS
4	FIRST CITY MONUMENT BANK
5	GUARANTY TRUST BANK
6	UNION BANK OF NIGERIA
7	UNITED BANK FOR AFRICA
8	ZENITH BANK